

METHODOLOGY OF UZBEK LANGUAGE AND LITERATURE TEACHING

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Abstract. After our republic gained its independence, the scope of scientific research on teaching the Uzbek language, that is, the state language, expanded significantly. In the past short period, doctor's and candidate's dissertations on the most important problems of mother tongue teaching were defended. This article deals with the methodology of teaching native language and literature.

Keywords: mother tongue, literature, psycholinguistics, pedagogy, technology, principle, teaching technologies

During the past centuries, many scientists have conducted many studies in the field of mother tongue and literary sciences. For example, A. Gulomov's "Increasing the educational activity of students in the process of mother tongue education" defended their doctoral theses in 1991, T. Ganiev's "Learning in the process of performing exercises in the mother tongue" in the same year activation of students' cognitive (perception) activity", Sh. Yoidosheva's "Consistency in teaching compound words in native language classes of Uzbek schools", K. Yusupov's "Formation of orthographic alertness in students of junior school age" in 1993 , M. Rajabova's "Education of friendship and kinship in students by teaching the dialect", N. Murodova's "Pronunciation and spelling errors caused by the local dialect in the student's speech and methods of correcting them", K. Yunusov's In 1994, a number of researches showed their reflection in "Formation of orthographic alertness in

students of junior school age", "Teaching the syntax of simple sentences to high school students of Uzbek schools by the discussion method" by M. Sobirova. began to find.

Expanding the creative thinking of students in native language and literature classes also depends on the methods of organizing the lesson. Lessons that are constantly repeated and use the same educational tasks over and over again make the student bored and bored.

Pedagogical technology of mother tongue education involves a complex process from setting the goal to evaluating the level of achievement of this goal, in which goals are a means of achieving a standard model. The current monitoring assessment is considered a factor that forms the educational process and acts as a link between the goal and its result.

According to the literature on pedagogical technology, in some foreign countries it is customary to set goals for students and teachers separately. In this case, the goals are set through the activity of the teacher (teaching, explaining, showing, telling, etc.), and the results expressed in the student's actions are called educational tasks. Each goal is made into a focus so that these tasks can be measured, defined, and repeated.

It is possible to explain that the native language teaching technology is an active participant in the student's educational process by involving him in the following types of activities in each lesson device: observing language phenomena; search, follow the sequence of events; compare events; identifying similarities between events; identify differences between events; determining the relationship between events and related events; practical application of events.

This type of independent activity is explained by the occurrence of the goal of mother tongue education in the course of a regular lesson. Today, the analysis of the expression of goals, which are reflected in the new pedagogical technology of mother tongue and literature with its own aspects and characteristics, shows that in

mother tongue education, it is expected to achieve its own result in each lesson, starting from the setting of the goal.

The educational principle of education implies bringing the young generation to maturity in all aspects. In the process of learning mother tongue and literature, students are inculcated with positive characteristics such as national ideal, loyalty to Motherland, love for nature, respect for people, respect, kindness, fairness.

The principle of harmony of education, upbringing and development in teaching the mother tongue. At the school, students are armed with a series of scientific knowledge that is very necessary in the field of phonetics, lexis and grammar of the mother tongue. They are provided with the necessary skills and competencies in the spelling, pronunciation, and correct use of punctuation marks in the written speech. At the same time, native language classes are also a means of educating and developing the student's personality.

The principle of scientificity and comprehensibility in teaching literature. The principles of scientificity of education and comprehensibility for children are interconnected and complementary didactic categories.

The principle of systematicity and consistency in mother tongue teaching. It is known that the mother tongue as a subject of study consists of a certain system. This system includes phonetic, lexical, grammatical aspects of the Uzbek language. In addition to the fact that the elements that make up this language system each have their own characteristics, they are integrally and closely connected with each other. It goes without saying that it is impossible to learn the grammar of a language without studying its phonetics at school. Only the student who has sufficiently mastered phonetics and graphics will master the lexicon thoroughly. When the vocabulary is thoroughly studied, it becomes easier to learn word groups. Therefore, the study of language phenomena in their interrelationship is considered the main tool that ensures its effectiveness.

The principle of connecting theory with practice in teaching mother tongue and literature. In the teaching of mother tongue and literature, we mean to connect theory

to practice, to ensure that students apply the scientific-theoretical knowledge they acquire from language, to arm them with practical skills necessary for independent life. Linking theory to practice, turning literature and mother tongue teaching into useful goals. Subjecting the studied language phenomena to the development of students' speech activity means connecting language education with life, with everyday life, with people's work activities.

Principles of consciousness, activity and independence in mother tongue teaching. Consciousness in didactic literature means a reasonable acquisition of the content of information related to the studied topic, a deep and comprehensive understanding of conclusions and generalizations, a systematic and correct presentation of knowledge on the topic, the transformation of the acquired knowledge into confidence and belief, independence from the learned knowledge in life. is understood to be able to use it. This principle requires understanding and conscious mastering of the essence of language phenomena.

The principle of consciousness. Consciousness is a principle aimed at conscious reduction of knowledge. It has the following features:

- to determine the main purpose of education, its necessity for life;
- conscious acquisition of evidential materials and ability to distinguish between them;
- learning, strengthening, repetition of knowledge;
- educates on the ability to evaluate acquired and self-achieved results.

Therefore, the basis of the principle of consciousness in the methodology of teaching the mother tongue allows you to understand the meaning and content and to perform practical tasks such as asking, listening, reading, writing, etc. .

Awareness of mother tongue education is based on the following principles:

- 1) Increase vocabulary and work on spiritual groups.
- 2) Ensuring logical consistency in expressing opinions.

To be able to use the expressive possibilities of the language correctly and appropriately, in accordance with speech situations.

In addition to the study of literature, the introduction of the system of linguistic and psychological educational tasks to the education of the mother tongue, to fulfill the need for independent observation in the mind of the student, to choose words and express an opinion, to form skills and competencies, and the skills of speech activity. serves to expand lamina.

The classification of mutual relations in the student-education-teacher system is as follows: according to the requirements of DTS, the student as an active subject of the educational process should search for himself, observe, differentiate, analyze and classify language phenomena. should make, conclude. Only by working with such methods can we form and develop independent and creative thinking in students.

Only then, the student learns not to rush to express an opinion, to make independent observations, to think about every word before speaking, to choose words suitable for the situation and to use them appropriately in his speech. He develops a sense of responsibility for words, gets used to speaking concisely, fluently and clearly.

Organizing independent work in classes, based on the nature of the problems, questions, assignments, manages the educational process, educates independence and activity in the young generation. And this:

- forms and develops the skills of using acquired knowledge in practice;
- students strengthen their confidence in their own strength and knowledge;
- knowledge, along with the creation of a clear emotional image, leads to the understanding of the essence of definitions and classifications, to the mastery of the imagination at the level of understanding.

In native language classes, the main attention should be focused on independent and coherent expression of the product of creative thought in the students, and on increasing the vocabulary.

Summary

The effectiveness of teaching the mother tongue largely depends on its connection with literature, or vice versa. In fact, my mother tongue is also studied in literature classes. For example, during the analysis of the language of an artistic work, the stylistic significance of some grammatical form, the significance of synonyms in speech is explained, etc.; pupils and students get acquainted with various means of expression of the language. Work carried out in a certain consistency on the language of the work of art will increase the vocabulary of my student and student. As a result of the works performed in the classroom and outside the classroom on the visual means of literary speech, readers and students will gain a broader understanding of the word and its role in different speech styles. Various glosses of expression help to understand the aesthetic effect and importance of language in a deeper way. The mother tongue is considered an important "key" for thorough mastering of all subjects studied in secondary schools, academic lyceums and vocational colleges. Pupils and students learn other subjects through the medium of language. By expressing his thoughts in writing and orally in all subjects, he also learns his native language perfectly.

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